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*Poems,
Essays,
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and Others*

A DAY IN THE LIFE OF A PH.D.

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Hey, I just graduated ranked 1st in my batch,
but who would have thought that I started with doubts in mind?
doubt if I am going to make it through the trimester
doubt if I can finance all the things that are needed for a Ph.D.

For the past years, coffee has been my best friend
PDFs and research are my confidants
eyebags are the witness of my 2-3 hours of sleep
Not just that, Efficascent products and the like fight alongside me

All those years, it was a mix of success and failures
persistence and hesitations
faith and disbelief
And of course, I, trying to do things and never giving up

In the end, I realized that it was not me alone,
But it was, and it will always be God
I graduated with flying colors
A great reminder of the fruit of my labor and the intervention of God